

THE PERCEPTION OF PARENTS OF BRGY. CALUMPANG TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPREHENSIVE SEXUALITY EDUCATION

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Abstract

Section 11 of the Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2012 states that “The State shall provide age- and development-appropriate responsible parenthood and reproductive health education to adolescents and school-age children which shall be taught by adequately trained teachers and educators in formal and non- formal educational system” (Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act No. 10354, 2013). The researchers believe that parents should play active roles on teaching their children about sex, and since the Comprehensive Sexuality Education is being implemented in schools pursuant to DepEd order issued last July 2018, this study focused on the assessment of the readiness, perception, and the socio-cultural factors that affect the readiness of six (6) parents with children age 10-19 years old living in Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina City. The qualitative study utilized a two-part guide questionnaire constructed by the researchers used in one-on-one recorded virtual semi-structured interviews. The data collected was analyzed and the researchers used coding and thematizing to link these data into cohesive overarching themes. This study revealed that all parents are willing to be the main source of information of their children about sex because they are aware that it is their responsibility as parents to do so. Taking into consideration that sex is a taboo topic, the study showed that socio-cultural factors like religion, tradition, and culture do not seem to affect the way parents perceive the importance of sex education. However, it was revealed that parents have varying levels of readiness to teach their children about sex education. Embarrassment and lack of knowledge about sex seem to be barriers in teaching their children about sex. Therefore, the assistance and support of teachers, the LGUs, and other stakeholders in educating both the parents and the children about CSE is of importance to raise awareness and encourage open discussions about sex among parents and students alike.

Keywords: Comprehensive Sexuality Education, readiness, socio-cultural factors, perception, qualitative research, Philippines

Introduction

Sexual Health Education (SHE) plays a vital role in society, knowing SHE will help people to create, promote, and develops goals addressing universal access to reproductive

health (UNFPA, 2011). According to UNESCO (2018), Sexual and Reproductive Health (SRH) focuses on the issues of puberty, pregnancy, access to modern contraceptives, unsafe abortions, and violence including gender-based violence affecting adolescents. Adolescence is a stage where the person is

growing, learning, and developing social independence. Without adequate knowledge and preparation, adolescents are vulnerable to engaging in early sexual intercourse that can lead to several consequences like teenage pregnancy, getting infected with sexually transmitted diseases, unsafe abortion, and sexual abuse. Also, women with adolescent pregnancies experience more abortions, cesarean sections, and stillbirths in their lifetime (Yussif, 2017).

An estimated two million Filipino women, ages 15 to 49 years old, are expected to get pregnant this year as a result of the COVID-19 Lockdowns, said the Commission on Population and Development (POPCOM) in 2020. In the study of the University of the Philippines Population Institute and The United Nations Population Fund, it states that 10 percent of these pregnancies will be among women ages 20 years old and below. As per the Department of Health, from April to June 2020, there were 934 newly confirmed HIV-positive individuals reported to the HIV/AIDS & ART Registry of the Philippines (HARP). The country has an increasing incidence of teenage pregnancy, sexual violence, and HIV cases that brought a lot of attention to the government and the people of the country.

The Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2012 or R.A. 10354 firmly states that the state shall provide age- and development-appropriate responsible parenthood and reproductive health education to adolescents and school- age children which shall be taught by adequately trained teachers and educators in formal and non-formal educational system and integrated in relevant subjects. The Law's Implementing Rules and Regulation mandates the Department of

Education (DepEd) to integrate into its curriculum complete, accurate and relevant age- and development-appropriate information on responsible parenthood and reproductive health, respectful of culture and religious convictions, for integration across all subjects, key areas. In 2018, the government of the Philippines introduced Comprehensive Sexuality Education. To curb the rising incidences of teenage pregnancy, sexual violence, and STI's in the Philippines, Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) will be included in the academic curriculum in the ordinance of DepEd Order No. 31, series 2018 (DO 31). Endorsed for plenary approval by Sen. Risa Hontiveros and passed in August 2018, the Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) aims to normalize discussions about adolescent sexuality and reproductive health and to remove the stigma from all levels and will be applied to all learners of public and private elementary, junior and senior high schools, and of learning centers for Special Education and Alternative Learning Systems (ALS) and laboratory schools of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and local Universities (LUCs) except when certain provisions apply only to public schools. CSE aims to ensure all learners are equipped with comprehensive and accurate information that can advance gender equality and improve the learners' knowledge, values, attitudes, and skills to decrease risks related to poor health outcomes.

Parents are in the best position to teach sexuality education to their children. While the government and the schools also have the responsibility of teaching students about sexuality education, parents play a primary role in disseminating sexual information-through words, behaviors, and values they

convey (Ashcraft and Murray, 2017). Everything that children should learn about themselves for their well-being should start from their homes, and additional information from schools will only be supplemental. However, discussing sexuality education at the family level has been difficult for both the adolescent and the parents. One of the common concerns of parents in discussing sex education with their children is that they fear that dissemination of information about sex will lead to early sexual engagement of adolescents and privation of innocence. Some think it is contrary to their beliefs or religion. Embarrassment and stigma can also be considered as a barrier and the culture that taught them that sexual discourse is a taboo.

In this backdrop, the researchers will look into the sociocultural readiness of parents in Barangay Calumpang, Marikina City, to the implementation and roll-out of CSE. Calumpang is WCC's partner community. As researchers, the team would want to draw possible measures to help this community with their readiness for the implementation of CSE by understanding their socio-cultural readiness. Marikina City that has a 450 741 population and represents 3.42% of the total land area of Metro Manila. It is known as the Philippines' Shoes Capital with 2 150 hectares composed of 16 barangays divided into two districts (Marikina City - Shoe Capital of the Philippines, 2020). Under District 1 Barangay, Calumpang is included, has a lot area of 80.29 sq. km, a population of 14 857 (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2015), and it represents 3.30% of the total population of Marikina. About 17.59% of the population is from ages 10 to 19 years old (PhilAtlas, 2015). Looking into its history, Marikina City has been one of the bases of Roman Catholic missions which

the Augustinians and Jesuits established to build a chapel. Our Lady of the Abandoned Church is completed in 1572, also known as the Nuestra Sen ora de Los Desamparados is the patron saint of Marikina (Marikina City, Shoe Capital of the Philippines, 2021). In addition, in terms of religion, 85-90% of their total population consisted of Catholics. The other 10-15% consisted of other religions like Born Again, Dating Daan, and Jehovah's Witnesses. Their social gathering or celebration is the Barangay Day held on June 9, and the Fiesta of St. Anthony de Padua held every June 30, which is led by the Church (PhilAtlas 2015).

Methodology

Methodological Perspective

To satisfy the objectives of the study, a qualitative approach was applied. A qualitative study is appropriate when the goal of the research is to explain a phenomenon by relying on the perception of a person's experience in a given situation (Stake, 2010). The nature of this study is to understand the socio-cultural readiness and perception of parents about sex education, hence, a qualitative approach will be the most appropriate choice.

The researchers gathered data through semi-structured interviews with parents. According to DeJonckheere and Vaughn (2019), semi-structured in-depth interviews are commonly used in qualitative research and are the most frequent qualitative data source in health services research. This method is helpful if a researcher wants to get in-depth information from their respondents, exploring deep

feelings, getting up close and personal that is especially useful for sensitive topics.

Context of The Study

To curb the rising incidences of teenage pregnancy, sexual violence, and STI's in the Philippines, Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) will be included in the academic curriculum in the ordinance of DepEd Order No. 31, series 2018 (DO 13) that aims to educate the students about the different issues regarding sex education such as gender equality, family planning, gender sensitivity, etc. This evaluated the parents of adolescents' readiness to the implementation of CSE by asking questions in a semi-structured manner about their perception and socio-cultural factors that affect their readiness to the implementation of CSE. Three (3) mothers and three (3) fathers were individually to get an in-depth understanding of the said topic. The participants' sampling size for this study is to consider the researchers' timeline and limited resources due to the pandemic. The researchers sought to understand and interpret rather than to generalize to get the diverse and rich data. The participants to the study were from Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina, which is the researchers' adopted community. Snowball sampling was in identifying the participants. Interviews were conducted through virtual means due to restrictions implemented under enhanced community quarantine.

Participants of The Study

The participants who took part in this study were 3 mothers and 3 fathers from Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina, whose child is an adolescent 10-19 years old. Participants should be of legal age and have no cognitive

impairment. Respondents were reached and interviewed through snowball sampling. It was assured that the consent of the interviewee was obtained before the actual interview since this is considered a sensitive topic. Participants were free to withdraw anytime and confidentiality and anonymity will always be observed throughout the duration of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The participants needed for this study are parents of adolescent children aged 10-19 living in Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina since it is the researchers' adopted community. The researchers made use of the linkages available to them to contact target respondents. A letter was sent to the officials of Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina asking for their consent to let the researchers conduct a study with their residents. Three (3) mothers and three (3) fathers using snowball sampling were interviewed on a confidential one-to-one approach through virtual means and asked a set of semi-structured interview questions regarding their readiness and perception of the implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education in schools. Before the interview started, the purpose of the study was explained and consent was obtained. Likewise, the researchers sought permission from the participants to record the interview. A guide questionnaire devised by the researchers was utilized to gather data from the respondents. The first part of the questionnaire was all about the participants' demographic profile, which includes: age, sex, religion, and highest educational attainment. The second part of the interview made use of a guide questionnaire, with open-ended questions regarding their perception about the implementation of sex education and the socio-cultural factors that

affect their perception. Non-verbal cues such as facial expressions, tone of voice, and gestures were also observed throughout the interview. During the interview, there were two researchers present, one facilitated the interview and the other transcribed or documented the conversation between the interviewer and the respondent. Each interview lasted from 30 minutes up to 1 hour. These interviews were recorded and the respondents were informed before doing so. Interviews were conducted in a conversational method to invite opportunities to get in depth details from the participants. Due to the protocols implemented under community quarantine, the interviews were conducted through online means, e.g. Messenger. Interviews were recorded and transcribed for future analysis of data. By the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents was held of utmost importance and the data that was collected will only be used for research purposes.

Data Analysis Procedure

Recorded and transcribed interviews were examined for patterns and repeated ideas that emerge. The researchers did coding, categorizing and thematizing in treating the data to collected. Coding was used for the respondents in this study. The categorized information was linked together into cohesive, overarching themes. Secondary data from previous and related literatures and researches was utilized to support the findings and give meaning to the data collected.

Subjectivity of the Researchers

The researchers viewed this study in the naturalistic perspective where multiple realities can exist, and where both the

researcher and the respondents construct their own meanings and interpretations for each reality. As nursing students, the researchers believe that if comprehensive sexuality education is implemented, it will address high cases of teenage pregnancy, sexual violence, and sexually transmitted diseases (STIs) and give skills, attitudes, knowledge, and values that will develop respectful social and sexual relationships for better health choices. It is a good way to integrate health education and promotion, disease prevention, and risk reduction. To achieve this, the researchers also believe that parents should be active partners in teaching sexual education to students. Regardless of diverse personal values and experiences, raising sexually healthy children capable of engaging in healthy and respectful relationships should be given importance by parents themselves. To do this, parents should be able to comfortably and openly talk about sex and related topics, not in any vulgar or inappropriate way, but on the premise that they genuinely want their child to be informed and knowledgeable about the topic.

However, the researchers believe that a lot of sociocultural factors greatly affect the parents' stand on sexuality education. The Philippines, a country with diverse and conservative culture, has struggled to implement strategies to incorporate sexuality education into the academic curriculum, widely opposed by church leaders and conservatives. They believe that sexuality education will spoil the fragile nature of children and promote promiscuity among the youth. In opposition to this, the researchers personally believe that people should be more open to topics like sex to address issues that result from silence, and for

the people to stop treating it like a dark corner of society's bedroom.

The researchers believe that this study is timely and will help the parents be enlightened about this topic, and that lack of communication with their children on sensitive topics like these will lead to a multitude of problems. There is a saying, "Kabataan ang pag-asa ng bayan," so it is essential to focus on educating the youth about sexuality education. The researchers expect different reactions from parents, as this may be a complete shock for them since sexuality education is not something that they were concerned about and study about during their days in school. However, the topics in CSE are already briefly discussed in other subjects like Science, but CSE will pave the way for a more indepth discussion about sexuality education.

All that is mentioned above are from the student nurses' point of view. While the researchers believe that parents should play an active part in teaching sexuality education to the youth, the researchers needed to know the parents' stand on this topic – their perceptions, readiness, and the factors that affect their readiness to discuss such a topic with their children. It was expected by the researchers that they will get an honest opinion from parents as this concerns the health and well-being of their children. The results of this study will enlighten the researchers on why parents believe what they believe and say what they say, and hopefully, will serve as a guide to determine steps to encourage parents to be more open and ready to talk to their children about this sexuality education.

RESULTS

The purpose of this qualitative study is to gauge and assess the readiness and perception of six (6) parents in Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina City regarding the implementation of the Comprehensive Sexuality Education in schools and their parents' willingness to play an active role together with the teachers to teach their children about sex education.

The Republic Act No. 10354, also known as the Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2021 implements the inclusion of the Comprehensive Sexuality Education in both private and public schools. Section 11 of the said law states that "The State shall provide age- and development-appropriate responsible parenthood and reproductive health education to adolescents and school-age children which shall be taught by adequately trained teachers and educators in formal and non-formal educational system." Advocates of RH law stated that the access to reproductive health information is not just to define sex among the youth, but also to address different topics that are related to the issue like information about the different diseases that can be transmitted through sex, as well as the use of family planning methods and contraceptives (Abrigo & Paqueo, 2016).

Demographic profile of the Participants

The participants were composed of three mothers and three fathers. All participants were from Barangay Calumpang, Marikina City. Marikina City is a predominantly Christian community and 80% of its residences are Roman Catholics. The age of the participants ranges from 38-46 years old, and are all open to the implementation of CSE which supported the findings of Nurullah (2010), stated that parents in the middle-age groups of 30-39 years and 40-49 years (55.5%) have shown

more support and consideration for the implementation of sex education in schools. All the participants are parents of an adolescent 10-19 years old and are Roman Catholics. The Catholic Church has slowed down the implementation of the reproductive health in the Philippines for seven years (Yee, 2019). The Church and other religious groups with conservative thought about reproductive health hindered the implementation of sex education in the supreme court because one of the major reasons is about protecting the existence of the unborn child which is being neglected by teaching sex education and using of contraceptives (Yee, 2019). Because of the opposition and delay in implementing of the sex education, majority of the participants stated that they do not have enough knowledge about sexuality education. That is why they all agreed that it should be taught to their child to not repeat their mistake by getting pregnant at a young age. Catholic bishops were alarmed by the Philippine government planning to include the sex education in the country's basic education. Catholic Bishops believed that many schools in the Philippines are not appropriate in teaching reproductive health, doubting that a sensitive and delicate topic like sexuality education should be taught in the classroom. Catholic Bishops believed that implementing sex education in schools will just give them idea to have a sex with the use of contraceptives and condom. The church opposed in using contraceptive believing that using these abortifacients known as a sin against God (Saludes, 2016).

All participants were in favor of creating an open and safe space for young people to learn about sexuality and sexual health. Learning about these topics were recognized by the participants beneficial to the welfare and

wellbeing of their children, despite of their religion and culture. Majority of parents, and demographic groups all agreed and supported the implementation of complete sexuality education. All specific topics related to sexuality education received a huge support in including it to the curriculum even for those people who viewed this topic as controversial agreed in the implementation, proving that parents want a complete sexuality education for their children by rejecting the idea of abstinence-only education (Kantor, 2017). Parents believed that reproductive health should be taught without the influence of religion (Cameron, 2020). Across all groups, all parents were in favor of the provision of SRH education in schools and said that it was crucial to have sex education in schools. Parents mentioned that issues around CSE were not discussed openly in the majority of the homes as it is still considered a taboo, and thus, they felt that the schools were a good avenue to teach young people about CSE. Some parents stated that it is better to teach it inside the classroom because teachers are more knowledgeable in this kind of topic and they felt that their child will become more serious in learning in this kind of topic because of the trust they have for their proctors when it becomes to educating them. Parents also believe that religion has nothing to do with this topic.

The participants of this research whose highest educational attainment were high school graduates and vocational course graduate stated they do not have previous experience about sex education and have only limited information about CSE, which supports the study by Opara (2010) concluded that with a high level of education, understanding of sexuality education improved, and therefore

concluded that it is important to give focus and great consideration to the education of women so that they will be more equipped and ready to educate their children in the future. The higher the complexity of learning, the higher their understanding is.

Parents' positive reaction towards the implementation of CSE

Parents see sex education as vital in the development of values and healthy behaviors of their children. Parents perceived sex education as a solution to present timely problems faced by most young people and families like increasing teenage pregnancy. Parents were all in favour of the implementation of sex education in schools, stating that students would benefit from its inclusion on the academic curriculum, especially because students in this present era are more exposed to promiscuity through the internet and social media. Parents also stated that young girls would greatly benefit from the implementation of CSE in schools because they are the ones who can get pregnant at an early age. This will lead to a responsibility to bear and care for a child they are not possibly ready for. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2014), one in ten young Filipino women age 15 to 19 is already a mother or pregnant with first child. In 2019, girls aged 15 and below who is already a mother increased by 7% compared to 2018. The rising teenage pregnancies is the "main problem of the Philippines today," according to a survey in 2020 by the Social Weather Station.

The following are the themes and its contents that emerged from the results of the interviews conducted with the parents:

Table 1. Parent's perception the implementation of CSE

THEMES	CONTENTS
Experience on discussing Sex Education	Personal lived-experiences of parents Parent-adolescent relationship
Environment	Media Peer Influences
Readiness to talk about sex education	Family-level Community-level
Expectations for CSE	

Experience on discussing Sex Education. All participants shared their thoughts on how they were taught by the society with regards to sexuality education as adolescents themselves, and how they tried to be educators along sexuality and sexual health to their children as now parents. They admitted that they did not have much information or experience about sex education during their time as adolescents. Because it was a taboo, discussions about sex were not directly opened up at homes. In schools, parents stated that sex education is only limited to the anatomy of the reproductive system, the process of pregnancy, and birth. There was no mention of STDs, family planning methods, and the use of contraceptives. The only way they knew about sex is through peers. **A) Personal lived-experience of parents** were among the drivers why they see CSE as important solution to most issues faced by young people, like addressing teenage pregnancy. The chance of the parents while they were teenagers did not allow them to have better knowledge and understanding to CSE which created a gap for them to be better educators to their children in terms of their

sexual health needs. These findings are similar to a previous study in South Africa. According to Lukolo & Dyk (2015), parents did not attempt to discuss sex education with their children due to their lack of knowledge. Some parents did not attend school. They thought they will not give accurate information because, in their generation, there was no CSE, and the sex-related topic was not open to being addressed and identified as taboo. One of the main reasons schools did not implement sex education early in the Philippines is the Catholic Church's opposition to its implementation. About 86% of the Philippines' population is Catholic. Religious morals and influence are deeply incorporated in the political agenda and laws of the country, even pushing lawmakers to compromise and work with the Church to alter the principles of sex education. The Church believes that sex education will only encourage the youth of the Philippines to engage in promiscuous behavior and that education about sexual matters should always remain a family concern. Furthermore, the Church firmly believes that parents should only give information about sex, and it is up to them what and to what extent they are going to educate their children. Lastly, the Church believes that high birth rates are not why the country is one of the poorest countries in Asia, hence, their disagreement with the implementation of sex education in schools (De Guzman et al., 2011). **B) Parent-adolescent relationship** was seen to be critical in helping adolescents to develop values and improve critical decision-making skills especially along building an intimate relationship and engaging to sexual activity. Communication is a vital part of relating to one's child to be able to be open to them while talking to their children about sex. In the study

of Abdullah et al. (2020), some parents were shy and one of the barriers in discussing sexuality, and lastly, they thought that their children were still too young. Similarly to the study of Robinson et al. (2017), schoolchildren were too juvenile to know about sexual education. They fear that if children were exposed before they reach their "maturity" level, they will then have too much information early enough to handle that type of knowledge and handle it well.

Environment. All participants stated how their environment has contributed to their experiences and perceptions about sex education while they were growing up. They also shared their thoughts about how social media has greatly influenced the actions of their children towards sex, and how it poses as a threat to how their children perceive sex. Children nowadays are more exposed to promiscuity through the internet and social media. There is no doubt that students can use the internet to reinforce knowledge about specific topics and serve as a medium for enhanced learning. Still, excessive or unsupervised use posed disadvantages to the child and easily influence their behavior and thoughts. It led to risky behaviors and modify the students' capacity for healthy and successful relationships (Alfeche, 2017). **A) Media** was seen as a threat by parents and a number of factors may have contributed to this. First, the amount of time an adolescent spends time on the social media unsupervised by the parent. According to the data report Hootsuite (2021), Filipino people ages 13 years old and above has 74.1% of the 81.8 million population uses the internet. The average daily time spent on the internet using any device is 9 hours and 45 minutes and 4 hours and 15 minutes in using social media. Some contents on the

internet involve abusive video and comments, cyberbullying, and sexual harassment. Half of the parents did not know how to use content filtering and parental controlling settings. Some of the parents use screen time in able to minimize their child's internet usage. Second, its accessibility to a material that portrays sex (eg. Pornographic material). According to Pornhub Insights (2019), Filipino people spent about 13 minutes and 50 seconds using their mobile phones watching pornographic videos and making the Philippines included in the top 10 list. Despite the blocking on internet providers in some of pornography and Xvideos in the country with regards to antichild pornography. An estimated 28,258 users every second were watching pornography on the internet wherein compared to two decades ago, the spread of pornography increased so much. In all of internet downloads, 35% of these are pornography related and is probably the reason why the government of the Philippines tend to block sites regarding pornography to avoid users from visiting popular pornographic websites all over the world to block internet users from accessing the world's most popular pornographic websites. According to Adanza (2018), Pornhub was the site that most Filipinos visit which would be an average of 12 minutes and 45 seconds compared to other countries. Third, social media had the feature of being able to connect to a lot of people. Social media allowed one to connect to a vast network of people. A study by Landry (2017) in Washington concluded that high-frequency SMS and increased sexual activities through phone use have a positive, statistically significant relationship with each other. One of the main factors that significantly influenced adolescents' sexual risk behaviors is that social

media is an access to a more extensive peer network, where adolescents can interact with many people of different ages, whatever the distance may be. It increases their chance to talk to and interact in any form with a person who might already have an experience with sex, leading to discussions about sex. **B) Peer influences** have also substantial impact on the experience and perception of parents towards sex education. They stated that since it was not extensively taught at schools, they would talk to their friends about sex driven by curiosity. This curiosity led to self-exploration, leading to situations wherein young girls would get pregnant, and getting someone pregnant. Children who were curious about things were the children that were not allowed to find out about it. That is why they craved to know more. A study done in the Philippines had one respondent who was 15 years old and said that she and her friends often talk about sex in their house, friends who are already mothers, stating that conducting sexual activity hurts and at the same time makes you feel good. Most of the women in the study learned sex through their partners, who eventually learned it from their peers (Gregorio, 2018).

Readiness to talk about sex education. The participants interviewed had varying levels of readiness to talk to their children about sex education. **A) At the family-level**, some parents stated that they are 100% ready to teach their children about sex, saying they are the primary caregivers, and know their child best. Therefore, the responsibility of teaching children about sex must be shouldered by the parents. Some parents stated that they address sexuality in their home; however, it is only about reminding them about rights, wrongdoings, abstinence, and basic knowledge. Also, some parents were reluctant

because they have limited knowledge about it. Because of this, sometimes they were uncertain, but they know that their children need it, and they are willing to attain guidance from the teachers and school to have it discussed in an elaborative way. According to Ram et al. (2019), parents needed to collaborate teaching with a teacher to address sexuality education is a proper and extensive discussion. However, some of them do not open this topic at home because they are embarrassed. **B) At the Community-level,** teachers should be ready, and properly equipped with the right attitude and knowledge about sex. Their biases must be eliminated and should be able to teach age-appropriate, culture-sensitive knowledge about sex. Therefore, teachers must be properly trained since their knowledge about sex and other important matters is going to reinforce whatever is taught at the students' homes. According to a study by Kantor and Levitz (2017), sex education included a wide array of topics, and some may say it is comprehensive sex education. Since there are numerous topics to be covered in sexual education, teachers must be prepared mentally before diving into providing information. The preparation of the teachers is as necessary as the preparation of parents in teaching their children sex education and knowing that the school will be teaching sex education. If teachers are not in the right training, the students will not acquire the proper elements of sex education. The function of executives in Barangay indeed has relation towards teaching and learning process of sex education in society. There has to be participation in instructing the parents in the community to obtain a good understanding of the subject matter sexuality and the enforcement of CSE in

schools. Therefore consider that to carry out CSE effectively and then provide its significance to adolescents and their parents, who are their primary educators, teachers, and officials, must establish an efficient workforce. It is necessary that such stakeholders coordinate to ensure that the public receives reliable information to fulfill their desires and needs and perhaps to assist young people in developing sexually safe relationships free of judgment, insecurity, anxiety, and blame. To fully acknowledge, educators and policymakers should advocate both the subject and mode of delivery to offer sex education to these upcoming generations. (Zulu 2019)

Expectations for CSE. Parents' expectations towards Comprehensive Sex Education in schools is mainly focused on anatomical parts of the body with regards to sexuality and relationships, reproductive well-being, particularly HIV/STD prevention, pregnancy, and contraceptives. Because of the increased incidence of teen pregnancy, almost all of the parents believed that sexual orientation ought to be essential in the country's educational system and also because their children's generation has been so dissimilar to the parents' generation, they accept this form of educational opportunities in terms of teaching themselves to be aware with their sexual behavior that they will explore as they grow into adulthood, and that they could integrate into their future lives once they become parents to their children. Parents wanted to encourage their children to engage in this intervention ensuring that they must be completely aware of it and educated about certain topics. Family played an important role in their children's sexual lives when it comes to shaping their children's health choices and wellness. But nevertheless, there were a few

concerns that parents might not want to tackle with their children, including such sexual roles, because they were uncomfortable with it and did not know how else to explain it to them. It was also suggested that incorporating CSE into schools and making it accessible to the younger people would have a substantial impact on them. As a result, if they assess firstly the availability, the age of the children, and the norms that they possess before preparing to introduce sexuality relationships, beliefs, behaviors, abilities, human growth, and sexual reproductive health, this can be an adequate approach (Nogela, 2014).

The effect of socio-cultural factors to the perception of parents regarding CSE

The parents and the researchers have spoken by saying that sex education must not be dictated by their beliefs since it depends on each person or family to determine whether they want to eliminate taboo topics or to provide and promote sex education for their children. This infringement had also been identified in a number of nations, including Asia, Africa, and the Western Pacific. That being said, parents with limited information about sexuality would also like to be fully involved so that their children can be educated and informed about any of these topics, as shown by the fact that some people nowadays are becoming transparent in their initiatives to tackle this matter with their children, how values and practices from a household, as well as culture, still think that women tend to be virgins until marriage and far less physically engaging, whilst men tend to initiate and end the sexual interaction. Furthermore, using religious morals to have control over women's sexuality increased the means for men to reinforce their control over the family caused

the women to be confined to the domestic sphere of the family, and strengthened patriarchal controls over women (Gunasekara, 2017). The parents agreed that adolescents have to learn the broader and relevant issues addressed in sexual health, amid major barriers and opinions within every individual or family since adolescents were still developing, this may encourage them to reduce sexual encounters, establish healthy sexual practices, lessen teenage pregnancies, as well as avoid sexually transmitted infections. Most of the parents mentioned that their religion is Catholic and told that their beliefs never stopped them from guiding their child and the principles that they teach so if ever these might be implemented in schools, the schools should consider and incorporate the topics that will be discussed based on the student's knowledge and perception about sexuality and how they can apply it without getting involved into some sexual issues (Chi, 2012).

Conclusion

Adapting Bandura's Social Learning Theory, parents' socio-cultural readiness towards the implementation of CSE is determined by their personal factors, behavior, and environmental factors. Personal factors include the parents' perception towards CSE, their previous experiences with CSE, what they already know about it, and their expectations that come with it. Behavioral factors which surfaced in the study are how ready are they to teach their children about sex education, and the associated practices at homes with regards to sex education. While environmental factors drawn from the parents were the beliefs, traditions, and culture they have and how these affect their perception regarding CSE,

peer and media influence, and their suggested community measures to help them improve their knowledge and awareness about CSE.

- All participants were from Barangay Calumpang, Marikina City. The participants were composed of three mothers and three fathers. The age of the participants ranges from 38-46 years old, and are all open to the implementation of CSE which supported the findings of Nurullah (2010), stated that parents in the middle-age groups of 30-39 years and 40-49 years (55.5%) have shown more support and consideration for the implementation of sex education in schools. The participants of this research whose highest educational attainment were high school graduate and vocational course graduate. All the participants are parents of an adolescent 10-19 years old and are Roman Catholics. Marikina City is a predominantly Christian community and 80% of its residences are Roman Catholics.

- All parents agree that the implementation of CSE is a great way to educate students starting at a young age to be more mature and careful in their decisions to avoid engaging in early sex. They believe that CSE will teach them the right attitude and discipline to know the consequences of early sexual intercourse, as they believe that this will lead to economical and possible health problems in the future. They expect that CSE will teach their children the use of contraceptives and family planning methods, as well as good manners and right conduct to establish healthy relationships and learn necessary life skills.

- Parents' socio-cultural readiness towards the implementation of CSE is determined by their personal factors, behavior, and environmental factors. Personal factors

include the parents' perception towards CSE, their previous experiences with CSE, what they already know about it, and their expectations that come with it. Behavioral factors which surfaced in the study are how ready are they to teach their children about sex education, and the associated practices at homes with regards to sex education. While environmental factors drawn from the parents were the beliefs, traditions, and culture they have and how these affect their perception regarding CSE, peer and media influence, and their suggested community measures to help them improve their knowledge and awareness about CSE. Socio-cultural factors like religion, beliefs, and tradition does not seem to affect how the parents perceive the importance of CSE in adolescents, stating that their generation is a lot different from their children's generation and that cultural and religious beliefs should not dictate how parents want their children to be educated.

- In Addition, the WCC College of Nursing will integrate awareness-raising activities and advocacy activities in its community extension efforts in Brgy Calumpang, awareness-raising can be in form of educational discussions with parents like conducting health education sessions and seminars with the residents of Brgy. Calumpang as the audience. The seminars' ultimate objective is to empower and ready the parents for CSE and how they can teach it to their children. Thus, the support of teachers, the government, and other stakeholders is important to reinforce the knowledge of both the parents and the children to be able to be fully informed and aware of CSE

Figure 3. Adapting the social learning theory

The study provides insight to the needs, expectations, and perception of parents about the implementation of CSE in schools. All parents agree that the implementation of CSE is a great way to educate students starting at a young age to be more mature and careful in their decisions to avoid engaging in early sex. They believe that CSE will teach them the right attitude and discipline to know the consequences of early sexual intercourse, as they believe that this will lead to economical and possible health problems in the future. They expect that CSE will teach their children the use of contraceptives and family planning methods, as well as good manners and right conduct to establish healthy relationships and learn necessary life skills. Socio-cultural factors like religion, beliefs, and tradition does not seem to affect how the parents perceive the importance of CSE in adolescents, stating that their generation is a lot different from their children's generation and that cultural and religious beliefs should not dictate how parents want their children to be educated. Parents, however, have varying levels of readiness to play an active role in educating their children about sex. Embarrassment and lack of experience and knowledge about sex

seems to be a barrier in talking to their children about sex. On the other hand, some parents are 100% ready to have open discussions about sex to their children, stating that it is their responsibilities as parents to be the primary educator of their children and that any knowledge they obtain outside their homes should only be supplemental. Parents have different levels of readiness regarding assuming an active role in teaching their children about sex, but all parents expressed their willingness to take part in doing so, stating that it should be the parents who will have to be the main source of information of children about sex and other life skills. Therefore, the support of teachers, the government, and other stakeholders is important to reinforce the knowledge of both the parents and the children to be able to be fully informed and aware of CSE.

Adapting Pender's health promotional theory, parents' socio-cultural readiness toward implementation of CSE is determined by their individual characteristic and experiences including their different age group and their knowledge and perception in including CSE to school curriculum. Behaviorspecific cognition and affect include expectations of parents and adolescents in implementing CSE in schools, consideration of taboo's by not discussing CSE openly at home, and religious belief. Behavioral outcomes include parents' willingness to be the primary educator to their child, favor in creating an open and safe space to learn CSE, and seminars that can educate parents and measures their knowledge toward comprehensive sexuality education.

Implications

Table 2. Community approach to educate parents about CSE

THEMES	CONTENTS
A whole community approach	Role of parents Role of education institution Role of government
Seminars as measures to educate parents	

A whole community approach. All the participants suggested what community measures or programs can be implemented to help other parents and students' to be more aware, knowledgeable of, and open to discussions at homes about sex. **A) The Role of parents** does not just lie on being the one responsible for the education at home of children about sex. To be able to play the role of being primary educators about sex, parents will also have to stay informed and aware of CSE if they intend to educate their children about sex. A parent suggested that one way of educating parents is to conduct seminars in barangay to be able to educate parents about what CSE really is, misconceptions about sex education, and ways on how to communicate with their children about sex. As stated in a research of American Academy of Pediatrics, health care professionals, educators including the policymakers can help the parents and the youth in offering awareness, training and motivation about sex education which includes the ability to communicate about sex, to determine and actively participate, and to comprehend the social risk and protective factors that regulate sexuality discussion, including such cultural rules that prohibit or promote interaction. This community-based

initiative would have a greater impact on family relationship, resulting in an improvement in the adolescent's actions and increased parental abilities to improve nurturing strategies at home regarding topics about sex education. The researchers believe that all the respondents recommended community activities like seminars to help them expand their information and understanding about sex education as community members such as local workers and community health professionals are knowledgeable about these matters and so would be able to direct and instruct them in an effectively and efficiently manner. Everyone associated with the implementation should perform their duties. To help avoid sex-related issues, parents should help their children by instilling appropriate knowledge about certain things and guiding them when their children have concerns; Local officials will implement programs in various barangays to encourage all individuals in spreading knowledge and increasing awareness about sexual health (Breuner & Mattson, 2016). **B) The Role of education institutions** is to reinforce and add supplemental knowledge about CSE to the students. And so, these institutions need to have the proper facilities and teachers who have undergone training to be able to educate children about sex. Prior to actually teach sex education for all learners, educational institutions should prepare and coordinate everything that is allocated, including the resources needed; teachers who will bring out their utmost, understanding, and capabilities in teaching their students, and who would not only be compliant but also flexible, despite as to how sensitive the content is; and lastly, the government will engage in the reinforcement of Comprehensive Sexuality Education in

schools by planning the relevant aspects to be addressed to students, training teachers prior going through the process, also establishing guidelines throughout all areas ensuring that there are still limitations in incorporating this sort of education in schools (Breuner & Mattson, 2016). In particular, the CDC stated that ensuring educators with the resources they need to promote learning sexual and reproductive health concepts, along with strong support as needed and comprehensive development help, is necessary. Moreover, the dedication and the convenience in delivering sex education of educators had such an impact on their teaching skills. Trainings on teaching these topics must provide a strong evidence, expertise and qualifications and should emphasize the importance of reliability of this CSE program to the teachers. To introduce CSE in schools, first and foremost, schools must have appropriate facilities and resources for teaching sex education and teachers must have practical skills and abilities in delivering certain discussions to their students. C) The Role of the government is to make sure that the needs of its people are met, including the community's need to be educated about CSE. Seminars can be implemented by the LGUs as suggested by the parents interviewed. In accordance with the Republic Act 10354: The Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act of 2012 which states an act providing the human rights of all persons including their right to equality and non-discrimination of these rights, the right to sustainable human development, the right to health which includes reproductive health, the right to education and information, and the right to choose and make decisions for themselves in accordance with their religious convictions, ethics, cultural beliefs, and the

demands of responsible parenthood. In establishing and making policies, the government should ensure equal access to reliable, legal, accessible, and high-quality reproductive health care services, as well as appropriate information and education, including family planning and contraceptive methods, and should allow individuals to use resources to enhance the appropriateness of actively engaging from every community. The LGUs and community leaders should collaborate in proposing seminars in each barangay, which should then be prepared and implemented in a coordinated and responsible manner. Every household in the community expects professionals to instruct them, even their children, towards sexuality education since they have the authority and expertise to carry out the program and effectively implement it.

Seminars as measures to educate parents. The participants suggested seminars to take place in their barangay to help them be more enlightened about CSE and so that both parents and their children will be educated about sex education. It was emphasized in the findings the need for village actions. This can be an area for potential partnership of school to the partner community in developing programs which the village can implement. According to the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (2016), the accuracy of information that should be supported and the implementation of appropriate sexuality education programs changes considerably. Assessments of the physiological aspects of sexuality education programs, including pregnancy rates and STIs, is very complex, and can be inaccurate because it depends on the behaviours of an individual to establish its efficiency. It is also stated that community-

centered activities would be a relevant component of a comprehensive approach because collaboration seen between community and educational institutions can demonstrate an effective opportunity to execute CSE and help educate these concepts to the youth. As per data analysis, the utilization of evidence-based teen pregnancy prevention treatments and reproductive health services in creative and community programs has greatly decreased pregnancy rates among African Americans and Hispanics under 15–19 years old. Sexual health, sexual engagement, including sexual relationships, gender identity, and sexual orientation, as well as how to avoid having STDs and unplanned pregnancies, should be the objective of these programs. A few states had already decided to respond to requests from parents and communities aim of providing education not just on pregnancy prevention, as well as on contraceptive methods, STIs (including the human immunodeficiency virus [HIV]), and in making use of condoms. Although report shows however not all programs are similarly efficient with all aspects, researches have shown reduced rates of sexual activity participation. The help and support of experts such as Obstetrician-Gynecologists or other medical professionals can play a significant role in guiding and teaching individuals for any such sexuality education programs, particularly in the community, since they are highly skilled with these and could perhaps monitor them because of the opportunity that has been provided.

In the light of the foregoing findings and conclusions the following recommendations are hereby given by the researchers for future researchers:

- In order to get more in-depth details about the parents' perception about the implementation of sex education, the researchers recommend interviewing more parents who have more diverse backgrounds in order to get more data and formulate not a generalization, but rather an understanding to their reasons and opinions on these matters. Due to the lack of resources and time, the researchers were only able to reach six parents with similar backgrounds from Brgy. Calumpang through snowball sampling. Therefore, it is more favourable to reach more people who represent different backgrounds to get more diverse data that can be analyzed and given meaningful interpretation.
- Since this research was conducted in the middle of a pandemic, the researchers interviewed the participants through virtual means only. Interferences like noise and slow internet connection played a big factor in collecting data from the participants. Due to these interferences, the researchers often asked for clarification of statements and this consumed a great amount of time. While online interviews can be useful especially in times like this where it is ideal to work at a distance from each other, face-to-face interviews would better capture the interaction between the participant and the researcher. Faceto-face interactions help build rapport and trust between the two persons involved and this would lead to the researcher getting more in-depth details from the person being interviewed.
- Due to lack of resources and time, the interviews were conducted only once with each participant. Exposure to the person and the data is important to analyze the data collected and to interpret it more accurately.

Therefore, the researchers recommend that future researchers spend more time with the participants conducting interviews not just once, but until all the data from the participant has been uncovered.

- This research has focused on the perception and the socio-cultural factors that affect the parents' perception regarding sex education. While it was assumed at first that the parents' religion and beliefs greatly affect how they perceive the implementation of sex education, the interviews uncovered that any tradition or belief that they have did not affect their perception about sex education in any way. For further research, the researchers recommend asking the participants what the specific barriers or hindrances are that affect their ability to talk to their children about sex, be it a socio-cultural factor or not. Asking this will help the researchers get to the root of the problem and recommend future actions that can be implemented to improve their knowledge and awareness about sex education.

- Other than Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina City, the researchers recommend to conduct this study in other places especially in areas where there are rising cases of teenage pregnancy, increased prevalence of STDs, a high number of sexual harassment and violence etc. Data collected from this research will enable the researchers to get to the roots of the problem and propose future plans that can be implemented to alleviate the problem.

The following are recommended to the LGUs and other stakeholders concerned with the implementation of CSE in schools to improve the knowledge and awareness of parents about CSE:

- From the data collected through interviews, it is safe to say that seminars conducted by the LGUs would help the parents be more open and informed about sex education. Since the majority of parents do not have much information and experience about sex education, seminars will equip the parents with the right knowledge and attitude towards sex that they can impart to their children. Parents also have stated that they are willing to attend programs like that as long as the advocacy of such programs will be helpful to them and their children.

- From the data collected, volunteer educators who are trained in family counselling will also help parents be more open and educated about sex education. These sessions would allow for more flexibility among the discussions about sex, and can be tailored to fit each family's needs according to their background, perception, knowledge, previous experiences, and expectations.

- Since parents expect teachers to be their partners in educating students about sex education, teachers should receive adequate training so they will be equipped with the age-appropriateness, culture sensitiveness, correct information about sex that they will impart to the students once the CSE is being taught at schools by involving NGO and Non-NGO organizations well-acquainted with CSE to deliver lectures and trainings about key topics.

Figure 4. Framework for the community extension program with Brgy. Calumpang, Marikina City

In addition, for WCC College of Nursing to integrate awareness-raising activities and advocacy activities in its community extension efforts in Brgy Calumpang, awarenessraising can be in the form of educational discussions with parents like conducting health education sessions and seminars with the residents of Brgy. Calumpang as the audience. The seminars' ultimate objective is to empower and make ready the parents for CSE and how they can teach it to their children. Key topics in seminars will include (from RA 10354):

- a) Rights of the Child;
- b) Child Health and Nutrition;
- c) Child and Adolescent Development;
- d) Gender and Development;
- e) Life skills;
- f) Age-appropriate Sexuality Education;

- g) Population and development;
- h) Marriage and family;
- i) Prevention of STIs, including HIV (as provided by RA 8504 or the Philippine AIDS and Control Act of 1998); and j) Recognition and elimination of gender-based violence.

While advocacy activities can be extended by WCC College of Nursing by engaging other stakeholders such as the LGUs, community-based groups like PTA, and high schools etc. with the following recommendations:

- Spiritual and social standards with explicit directives on sexuality and reproduction should be examined. Spiritual and social norms have a great influence on individual behaviour. That is why it is important to discuss how some aspects of one's belief, culture, and tradition affect their perceptions about sexuality.
- Heteronormativity, sexual orientation, and sex generalizations should also be discussed. Main thoughts regarding 'manliness' should be evaluated, and men and young men should be engaged with these projects. It is because the society has a set of norms about how one expects men and women to dress up, act and portray themselves that can serve as hindrances to reach their maximum potential to be able to do what they want, and how to function in a community where they can contribute. Gender stereotypes and main thoughts about masculinity should be discussed. And to achieve that, men and women should participate in this kind of program.
- Training the teachers is essential to have proper knowledge in expressing values and attitudes without bias in teaching CSE. DepEd order 31 s. 2018 which is the policy and

guidelines in the implementations of comprehensive sexuality education, the course outline is included, which will be the basis of the teachers' and it is their responsibility to introduce the topic and determine the goal and outcome of each lesson to their students.

- Students who will be exposed to CSE for the first time have to be guided well for CSE to be effective and taught properly. It would be useful if teachers will undergo training in order to practice their reactions to questions of the students and organizing peer support groups. Since the students are either of age to curiosity or arriving at that age, it is important for the teachers to discuss different ways to handle such circumstances.
- NGO workers who are equipped with CSE materials can be included to guide them in the delivery of their lectures of key topics. Not only is CSE a part of their school curriculum, it is also vital for their everyday lives.
- Using temporary gender separation in CSE programs as the first approach for the educators to address their concerns in delivering mixed gender education class. Separating the girls and boys for each class in terms of teaching comprehensive sex education can be a means to differentiate and effectively address the requirements and learning teaching styles, as well as helping the students learn in a comfort manner.
- Integrating experts in CSE, social training programmes, and gender issues in the school overview group. The involvement of a professional teacher, particularly a sex educator, and some other medical professionals who are experts in this area is significant since they are more knowledgeable of the background and concepts in sexuality

and therefore can deliver and foster sex education to the students and this might serve the institution in preparing for such improvement of educational abilities in educating CSE in terms of meeting curriculum objectives.

- Considering CSE a fundamental course in programming courses for educators in professional development. Since schools are also a significant source of information when it comes to students, CSE should be mandated to be included on the teacher's training. Educators must understand how to effectively educate youngsters in a comprehensive way in order to assure learning based on the sexuality education curriculum and because teaching sex education to children has a number of positive implications, such as enhancing young children's knowledge and altering their perspectives concerning sexual and reproductive health in and out of school.

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